

Supporting Information

for

Adding omalizumab to allergen immunotherapy in patients with asthma due to house dust mites: protocol for a randomized, 5-arm study

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1. Ethics

This trial is in compliance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association 2013), Good Clinical Practice, and the applicable laws of the country. The Bioethical Committee of Medical University of Silesia in Katowice (Poland) approved the protocol (BNW/NWN/0052/KBI/29/II/21/23). The Investigator will submit and, where necessary, obtain approval from the above parties for all substantial amendments to the original approved documents. Before screening, subjects will be asked to provide written informed consent. Suspected unexpected serious adverse reaction (SUSARs) will be subject to expedited reporting to the Competent Authorities and to the Ethics Committees, in compliance with the local regulatory requirements.

2. Study design

The trial will encompass 17 visits: 2 screening visits at the investigational site, six visits at the investigational site plus five follow-up calls while on therapy, then three visits at the investigational site and two follow-up calls during the one-year observation period after therapy discontinuation, and finally a follow-up visit at the investigational site at exit. A scheme of the timeline for all procedures is presented in **Table 1**. The eligibility of the subjects will be confirmed in the screening period. Subjects included in the trial (see below) will be randomized into five arms. During the screening visit, all subjects will receive a unique subject number. The subject number will be generated when the subjects' data are entered into the database by the coordinator of the study using a computer program. Randomization will rely on computer-generated numbers using Excel (v14.2.0, 2020 Microsoft Corporation). An Excel random number generator (Microsoft) was used to randomly assign patients to 5 arms with different interventions. The Excel RANDBETWEEN functions generate pseudorandom numbers from a normal distribution, in which the probability of all values that a random variable can take is equal. Each time Excel's random function is called, a new full list of patients is used, which returns a unique random sequence.

The primary evaluations will occur 24 months after randomization and 12 months after the follow-up period. Secondary assessment will occur 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 and 21 months after randomization. During the follow-up period, secondary evaluations will occur after 3, 6, and 9 months.

Prior trials evaluating the effects of combining omalizumab with HDM AIT (SCIT) were placebo-controlled and blinded.^{1,2} Placebo-controlled and double-blind designs remain the gold standard for determining the efficacy of AIT due to the high placebo effects observed. However, because of the combination of injectables (omalizumab) and tablet (SLIT) treatments, the present trial follows a non-blinded and open-label design. The lack of a placebo is more ethical and comfortable for patients. We exclude the placebo effect by using the 5-arm design, which is innovative and will allow for robust comparison among the arms.

Table 1. Visit schedule and procedures.

	Screening	Randomi- zation	Treatment period									Follow up period					
Visit Number	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10	V11	V12	V13	V14	V15	V16	V17
Visit Month	-3	0	1	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	25	27	30	33	36	1 mth FU
On site visit	x	x	x	x	x		x		x		x	x		x		x	x
Phone call follow up						x		x		x			x		x		
Informed Consent / Assent	x																
Demographics	x																
Medical/Allergy history	x																
Prior medications	x																
Concomitant medications ⁽¹⁾	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Skin prick test (SPT) ⁽²⁾	x						x				x					x	
Total IgE and HDM specific IgE, IgG4*	x						x				x					x	
Height and Weight measurements	x						x				x					x	
Asthma status (GINA)	x						x				x					x	
Physical examination*	x						x				x						
Spirometry* (FEV1)	x	x	x		x		x		x		x	x		x		x	
Biochemistry and Haematology ^(3, 4)	x	x					x				x					x	
Vital Signs ⁽⁵⁾	x	x	x	x	x		x		x		x	x		x		x	x
Pregnancy test (urine)* ⁽⁶⁾	x	x	x	x	x		x		x		x			x		x	
Inclusion / Exclusion	x	x															
Eligibility confirmed		x															
Randomization		x															
IP product		x (ch, dis)	x (ch, dis)		x (ch, dis)		x (ch, dis)		x (ch, dis)		x (ch, co)						
PEF meter* (daily)	x	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch, co)	
FeNO (optional)		x					x				x					x	
diary* (daily) ⁽⁷⁾		x (ch)	x (ch)	x	x (ch)	x	x (ch)	x	x (ch)	x	x (ch)	x (ch)	x	x (ch)	x	x (ch, co)	

	Screening	Randomi- zation	Treatment period									Follow up period					
Visit Number	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10	V11	V12	V13	V14	V15	V16	V17
Visit Month	-3	0	1	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	25	27	30	33	36	1 mth FU
ACT*	x (ch)	x (ch)		x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)									
ACQ*	x (ch)	x (ch)		x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)									
AQLQ*		x (ch)		x (ch)		x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)								
VAS*		x (ch)		x (ch)		x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)								
TASS		x (ch)		x (ch)		x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)								
TMS		x (ch)		x (ch)		x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)								
RQLQ*		x (ch)		x (ch)		x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)	x (ch)								
Blood sampling for immunological markers testing*		x					x				x					x	
Adverse events and concomitant medication*(8)		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

* performed at Early Termination Visit in case of premature withdrawal

¹ All concomitant medications will be collected at all visits including concomitant medications.

² SPTs will be performed by the same operator at investigation site to avoid inter-operator variability

³ Biochemistry include albumin, total protein, uric acid, sodium, potassium, calcium, phosphorus, chloride, bicarbonate, blood urea nitrogen, creatinine, lipase, amylase, magnesium, glucose, lactate dehydrogenase, alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, total bilirubin, alkalin phosphatase.

⁴ Haematology includes hemoglobin, hematocrit, platelets, white blood cells.

⁵ Vital signs measured in a sitting position include heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, respiratory rate and body temperature.

⁶ Urine pregnancy test must be performed on all females of childbearing potential. Female subjects are considered not to have childbearing potential before their menarche or if they have had a total hysterectomy or ovariectomy. Pregnancy testing may be repeated during the study at the discretion of the Investigator.

⁷ E-diary including asthma and rhinitis symptoms and rescue medication

⁸ All adverse events (AEs) will be evaluated at all visits including AEs/allergic symptoms from the onset until the event resolved or medically stable.

Abbreviations: ACQ, Asthma Control Questionnaire; ACT, Asthma Control; AQLQ, Asthma Quality of Life Questionnaire; ch, checked; co, collected; dis, dispensed; FEV1, Forced Expiration Volume in one second; FU, follow-up; mth, month; GINA, Global Initiative for Asthma; IgE, Immunoglobuline E; IgG4, Immunoglobuline; IP, Investigational Product; mth, month; PEF, Peak Expiratory Flow; TASS, Total Asthma Symptom Score; TMS, Total Medication Score; RQLQ, Standardized Rhinoconjunctivitis Quality of Life Questionnaire; SPT, skin prick test; VAS, visual analog scale

3. Trial population

A complete list of the inclusion and exclusion criteria is shown in **Table 2**. Asthma diagnosis will be based on the GINA criteria.³ Subjects meeting all of the inclusion criteria and none of the exclusion criteria will be considered eligible for the trial. Subjects will be advised in the informed consent form that they have the right to withdraw from the trial at any time. Subjects will be discontinued from the trial if meeting any of the circumstances shown in **Table 3**.

Consistent with GINA recommendations,³ which state that SLIT should be used in selected adult patients sensitized to HDM with persisting asthma symptoms despite low- to medium-dose ICS-containing therapy only if FEV1 is >70%, patients included in the trial will be required to show partial control of HDM-driven asthma with standard asthma therapies ($16 \leq \text{ACT} \leq 19$), and FEV1 >70% at baseline. However, few studies in the past have addressed the effects of SLIT alone in patients with moderate asthma. HDM allergy will be demonstrated with skin prick tests and serum concentration of allergen-specific IgE to *D. pteronyssinus* or *D. farinae* higher than 0.7 IU/mL. Although, ideally, the study should be conducted in monosensitized patients (or in patients sensitized to non-cross-reacting allergens), most people with allergies have polysensitization to multiple allergens. However, in this trial, any patients with a documented, physician-diagnosed, clinically relevant history of allergic asthma to perennial allergens and regular exposure to animal dander, molds, and/or cockroaches will be excluded.

Table 2. Selection criteria.

Inclusion criteria
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Age 18 to 65 years.2. Total IgE between 30-700 IU/mL (Poly-Check).3. Partially controlled with asthma therapies consistent with GINA treatment Step 3 or 4, with perennial symptoms confirmed as HDM-driven asthma based on medical history and positive nasal provocation tests.4. A score in the Asthma Control Test ≥ 16 and ≤ 19.5. Positive skin prick test results for <i>D. pteronyssinus</i>, and/or <i>D. farinae</i>.6. Serum concentration of allergen specific IgE to <i>D. pteronyssinus</i> or <i>D. farinae</i> >0.7 IU/mL (Poly Check).7. FEV1 >70% at baseline.8. Negative serum pregnancy test at screening for women of childbearing potential.9. Females of childbearing potential must be using highly effective and acceptable methods of birth control (as per the CTFG recommendations) to prevent pregnancy, and agree to continue to practice an acceptable method of contraception for the duration of participation in the trial.
Exclusion criteria
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Documented, physician-diagnosed, clinically relevant history of allergic asthma to perennial allergens and regular exposure to animal dander, pollen, molds, and/or cockroaches (e.g., present in the home, work, school, etc.).

2. Has experienced a life-threatening asthma attack (defined as an asthma episode that required intubation and/or was associated with hypercapnia requiring noninvasive ventilator support).
3. Clinical deterioration of asthma that resulted in emergency treatment, hospitalization, or treatment with systemic corticosteroids within 3 months prior to randomization, while on high-dose ICS treatment.
4. SLIT treatment with *D. pteronyssinus* or *D. farinae* within the last 10 years.
5. SCIT treatment with *D. pteronyssinus* or *D. farinae* reaching the maintenance dose within the last 10 years.
6. Ongoing treatment with any allergy immunotherapy product.
7. Severe chronic oral inflammation.
8. Any nasal or naso/oropharyngeal condition that could confound the efficacy or safety assessments (e.g., hypertrophy of the pharyngeal/palatine tonsils, clinically relevant nasal polyps, a history of paranasal sinus surgery or surgery of nasal turbinate)
9. Any clinically relevant chronic disease, including malignancy that in the opinion of the investigator would interfere with the trial evaluations or the safety of the subject.
10. History of eosinophilic esophagitis or with current severe or persistent gastroesophageal symptoms including dysphagia or chest pain that, in the opinion of the investigator, may constitute an increased safety concern.
11. A relevant history of systemic allergic reaction e.g. anaphylaxis with cardiorespiratory symptoms, generalized urticaria or severe facial angioedema that in the opinion of the investigator may constitute an increased safety concern.
12. Active or poorly controlled autoimmune diseases, immune defects, immunodeficiencies, immunosuppression or malignant neoplastic diseases with current disease relevance.
13. Requirement for continuous treatment with systemic corticosteroids for any indications.
14. Treatment with an investigational drug (SLIT and/or omalizumab) before study
15. Biological treatment in the last 60 days.
16. A history of alcohol or drug abuse.
17. Prior randomization into similar trial.
18. History or current evidence of any condition, treatment, laboratory values out of range, or other circumstance that in the opinion of the investigator are clinically relevant and might expose the subject to risk by participating in the trial, confound the results of the trial, or interfere with the subject's participation for the full duration of the trial,
19. Requirement for continuous treatment with β -blockers or with monoamine oxidase inhibitors.
20. Presence of rare hereditary problems of galactose intolerance, total lactase deficiency or glucose-galactose malabsorption
21. Lactation.

Table 3. Reasons for subject discontinuation.

Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If experiencing 3 severe asthma exacerbations within a 12 consecutive months period. - If experiencing severe or persistent symptoms of oesophagitis - Co-existing disease - Pregnancy - If, in the investigator's opinion, there is a connection between a SAE and the investigational drugs taken
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	- If, in the investigator's opinion, continuation in the trial would be detrimental to the subject's well-being
Withdrawal of consent	- An AE for which the investigator did not consider discontinuation from the trial necessary - Perceived insufficient therapeutic effect
Treatment with prohibited medication	- Any systemic glucocorticosteroids, (depot formulations parenteral administration, regardless of treatment days and dose)-14 days of wash-out - Immunosuppressive treatment (for example dupilumab or other biologics) - Long-acting muscarinic antagonists (LAMA) (e.g. Tiotropium) - Methylxantin (e.g. theophylline) - LTRA (e.g. montelukast, zafirlukast) - Other biological therapy
Other	- In case of protocol deviation, violation of eligibility criteria or deviation from the treatment plan specified in the protocol

4. Endpoints and assessments

Table 4 lists the primary and secondary endpoints and assessment methodologies. The evaluated variables are presented in **Table 5**. A physician will obtain the informed consent of all participants, evaluate inclusion and exclusion criteria, perform the physical examination, assess lung function and laboratory results, and evaluate all AEs and SAEs. All laboratory assessments will be conducted at a certified laboratory selected by the on-site investigator.

During the trial, the subjects will complete a paper diary. The following items will be outlined in the diary at pre-specified intervals during the trial: asthma symptoms by the use of the TASS scale, nocturnal awakenings due to asthma requiring SABA, use of asthma rescue medication, rhinoconjunctivitis symptoms by the use of the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), record AEs, and use of rhinoconjunctivitis medication.

Several questionnaires will be used to evaluate the secondary endpoints. In all cases, the baseline evaluation for questionnaires will be done during the randomization visit (V2).

The Asthma Control Test (ACT) is a patient self-administered tool for identifying those with poorly controlled asthma.⁴ The scores range from 5 to 25, with higher scores reflecting greater asthma control. An ACT score <16 indicates very poorly controlled asthma, scores of 16 to 19 not-well-controlled asthma, and scores 20 to 25 well-controlled asthma. The minimally important clinical difference is 3 points.⁵

The Asthma Control Questionnaire-5 (ACQ-5) consists of six questions on a scale from 0 to 6 of symptoms, on limitations due to asthma and symptoms in the previous week.⁶ A lower score corresponds with better asthma control. The proportion of participants with a minimally important difference (MID; defined as change >0.5) in ACQ

score without an increased dose of ICS or with no MID in ACQ score despite lower ICS usage at the end of the trial will be calculated.

The Asthma Quality of Life Questionnaire (AQLQ) is a 32-item questionnaire used to assess the physical, occupational, emotional, and social qualities of adults aged 17 to 70 with asthma.⁷ The AQLQ has four domains: symptoms (12 items), activity limitation (6 generic and five patient-specific items), emotional function (5 items), and environmental stimuli (4 items). The proportion of participants with a MID in AQLQ[S] score without an increased dose of ICS or with no MID in AQLQ(S) score despite lower ICS usage at the end of the trial will be calculated. In patients with allergic rhinitis, a visual analog scale (VAS) will also be used.

The Total Asthma Symptom Score (TASS) is a four-point symptom scale for asthma that analyzes cough, wheezing, breathlessness, and dyspnoea.

The Total Medication Score (TMS) is based on summed points: 1 point for inhaled corticosteroids, 2 points for short-acting beta-agonists, and 3 points for long-acting beta-agonists (separate or combined with ICS). Daily symptoms and medication scores will be monitored, after which mean monthly scores will be calculated.

The Rhinoconjunctivitis Quality of Life Questionnaire (RQLQ) will be administered optionally (when relevant). It measures the functional problems (physical, emotional, social, and occupational) that are most troublesome to adults (17-70 years) with either seasonal or perennial rhinoconjunctivitis of either allergic or non-allergic origin.⁸

Clinically relevant and medically confirmed asthma exacerbations will be defined as asthma worsening leading to at least one of the following criteria: doubling of ICS dose compared to background treatment minimum per 3 days, use of systemic corticosteroids for asthma symptoms for at least three days, emergency room visit due to asthma (requiring systemic corticosteroids), hospitalization (admission not required) for more than 12 hours due to asthma, or the annualized rate of clinically relevant asthma.

Regarding safety parameters, in addition to AE and SAE, all adverse events of special interest (AESI), such as AE leading to patient withdrawal, asthma exacerbation, especially anaphylactic reactions including anaphylactic shock, severe laryngopharyngeal reactions, autoimmune diseases, cancers, eosinophilic esophagitis will be monitored.

Table 4. Endpoints and assessments.

Primary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Change in mean daily dose of ICS after 24 months of therapy vs. baseline. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mean daily dose of ICS calculated for each patient as the average of the non-missing daily dose of budesonide (μg) over the two years of treatment. The baseline will be calculated over 3 months prior to randomization.
Secondary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disease control <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asthma Control Test (ACT). Change in ACT score of ≥ 3 points from baseline, or % patient with an ACT score of ≤ 19 points at baseline who had a post treatment score of ≥ 20 points Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ) Asthma symptoms-free days (without wheezing, coughing, breathlessness, and dyspnea) Long-term remission (>6 months without asthmatic symptoms) Change in ICS calculated over the last four weeks prior to visits compared to an equivalent baseline period before treatment start, long-term remission (defined as >6 months without asthmatic symptoms) Change in the GINA classification Number of emergency hospitalizations Number of asthma exacerbations (per year per subject during the 24 months of therapy and 12 months of follow up) Total Asthma Symptom Score (TASS) Total Medication Score (TMS) Patient quality of life <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asthma Quality of Life Questionnaire (AQLQ) Rhinitis Quality of Life Questionnaire (RQLQ)
Exploratory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Levels of serum markers in the course of therapy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>D. pteronyssinus</i> and <i>D. farinae</i>-specific IgE and IgG4 levels Lung function parameters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PEFR, FEV1, FeNO
Safety assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safety and tolerability during the entire treatment period assessed by TEAE, local and systemic reactions. Safety of the treatment on asthma parameters assessed by asthma related AEs and lung function tests. Following parameters will be monitored: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AE, SAE, Adverse Events of Special Interest (AESI) Laboratory: hematology, glucose, creatinine, complete blood count, CRP, potassium, sodium, liver function.

Table 5. Study procedures.

Variables	Items recorded
Medical history (past 2 years)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All asthma exacerbations (including visits to emergency rooms, hospitalizations) All changes in asthma treatment History of rhinitis, conjunctivitis, atopic dermatitis and food allergy Exposure to cigarette smoking
Concomitant medication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All concomitant medication (name of medication, dose, administration route and treatment period)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rhinoconjunctivitis and asthma medication - Changes in any concomitant medication
Medical examination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Height and weight - Vital signs (blood pressure and heart rate in a seated position) - Physical examination (skin, head, lymph nodes, respiratory, heart, abdomen, urogenital, musculoskeletal and neurological, general appearance). Pregnancy test if needed.
Lung function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forced vital capacity (FVC) and FVC percent predicted - FEV1 and FEV1 percent predicted - FeNO will be performed optionally in selected centers
Skin prick tests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive control: Histamine; negative control: Saline - HDM (<i>Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus</i> and <i>D. farinae</i>), cat (<i>Felis domesticus</i>), dog (<i>Canis familiaris</i>), mold (<i>Alternaria alternata</i>), grass (<i>Phleum pratense</i>), ragweed (<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>), tree (<i>Betula verrucosa</i>)
Laboratory tests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hematology: Erythrocytes, hemoglobin, hematocrit, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), platelets, leukocytes, neutrophils, eosinophils, basophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes. - Blood chemistry: Creatinine, urea, sodium, potassium, chloride, calcium, glucose, albumin, total bilirubin, aspartate aminotransferase (AST)/ serum glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), alanine aminotransferase - IgE: To confirm the diagnosis of allergy against HDM, blood samples will be drawn at the screening visit to determine specific IgE against <i>D. pteronyssinus</i> and <i>D. farinae</i>.
Questionnaires	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Asthma Control Test (ACT) - Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ) - Asthma Quality of Life Questionnaire (AQLQ) - Visual Analog scale (VAS) for patients with allergic rhinitis - Total Asthma Symptom Score (TASS) - Total Medication Score (TMS) - Rhinitis Quality of Life Questionnaire (RQLQ) (optional, when relevant)
Adverse events	(See Table 6)

5. Treatments and compliance

Subjects will continue on the asthma background controller treatment with low-dose ICS-formoterol or low-dose ICS-LABA (Step 3 GINA treatment) or medium-dose ICS-formoterol or medium/high-dose ICS-LABA (Step 4 GINA treatment) they were on before entering the trial. ICS tapering will be possible every three months during patient visits (step down 25%). However, for the research assessment, it will be considered after 12 months of treatment and after follow-up.

Patients treated with HDM-SLIT tablets will receive Actair® (Stallergenes Greer).⁹ This drug is indicated in adolescents (12-17 years) and adults for the treatment of moderate to severe house dust mite-induced allergic rhinitis or rhinoconjunctivitis, diagnosed by clinical history and a positive test of house dust mite sensitization (skin prick test and/or specific IgE).^{10,11} The daily dose of Altair® is one sublingual tablet,

preferably taken in the morning. The subjects will be instructed to take the tablet with dry fingers from the blister unit immediately after opening the blister and place it under the tongue, where it will disperse, avoiding any swallowing for 2 minutes. The first intake should be at the clinic (visit 3), with a minimum observation period of 30 minutes after the intake of 1 tablet (100 IR) for the recording of onset and duration of possible AEs. Before the first intake, an oropharyngeal examination will be performed, which will be repeated 60 minutes after drug intake. The second dose is two tablets (=200 IR), and then every day one tablet of 300 IR.

Patients treated with omalizumab will receive Xolair® (Novartis). Omalizumab is indicated for asthma control as adjunctive therapy in adults and adolescents ≥ 12 years of age with severe persistent allergic asthma who have a positive skin test or in vitro reactivity to perennial inhalant allergens and in patients with reduced asthma function, lung disease (FEV1 <80%) and frequent symptoms occurring during the day or causing awakenings at night, and who have repeatedly documented severe asthma exacerbations despite receiving high daily doses of inhaled corticosteroids in combination with a long-acting inhaled $\beta 2$ agonist.¹² The dosage of omalizumab will be 150 mg, administered subcutaneously every four weeks (from visit 2).

Rescue medication for asthma and rhinoconjunctivitis will be dispensed at the baseline visit. It consists of salbutamol 100 mcg dose, desloratadine tab 5 mg, mometasone furoate nasal drops 50 mcg per dose. The salbutamol inhaler will be used when necessary (2 doses four times per day).

Treatment may be discontinued for up to 7 days in case of oral surgery (including dental extraction and shedding of a deciduous tooth to allow healing of the oral cavity), inflammatory conditions in the oral cavity, upper airway viral infection, or other reasons if necessary by the investigator. If treatment is interrupted for more than seven consecutive days, the subject will contact the investigator before restarting the treatment.

Compliance will be assessed at each visit by SLIT-tablets counts. The investigator can exclude patients from the trial if compliance is less than 80% or more than 100%. To administer omalizumab, the patient will be trained to administer the drug and then use it themselves as directed every four weeks. Subjects will be informed to bring all residual and unused drugs and all empty packaging to the site at every visit.

6. Safety

The study will be conducted following the ICH-GCP guidelines. See definitions for safety parameters in **Table 6**. All AEs reported spontaneously by the subject or observed by the investigator or his staff will be recorded. The investigator will report all SAE and AESI

information (initial and follow-up), whether or not considered as related to the drugs under investigation, to the sponsor within 24 hours after obtaining it. The investigator will determine the relationship of AEs to the trial medication. The following definitions apply to the assessment of causality of an AE to the trial medication: not related, possible, and probable. The following standard with three grades will be used to measure the severity of all AEs, including abnormal clinical laboratory values: Mild (no disruption of normal daily activities), moderate (affect normal daily activities), and severe (inability to perform daily activities).

Local reactions (local swelling, pain, itching, or redness occurring following injections of trial medication) will be treated as AEs and graded as mild, moderate, or severe. Systemic reactions will be classified according to the World Allergy Organization grading system (**Table 7**).¹³

As clinical practice guidelines recommend, an Asthma Action Plan will be given to the subjects to provide guidance to manage the subject's symptoms. The investigator or designee will train subjects in their Asthma Action Plan. According to the Asthma Action Plan, subjects should contact the investigator when asthma symptoms increase or lung function is reduced. Signs and symptoms of asthma worsening include cough, wheezing, chest tightness or shortness of breath; waking at night due to asthma; or inability to do all usual activities, or increased need for reliever medication.

Table 6. Safety definitions.

Term	Definition
Adverse event (AE)	Any untoward medical occurrence in a patient or clinical trial subject administered a pharmaceutical product and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment.
Serious adverse event (SAE)	Any untoward medical occurrence or effect that at any dose: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results in death - Is life-threatening (this refers to an event in which the subject was at risk of death at the time of the event; it does not refer to an event that hypothetically might have caused death if it had been more severe) - Requires inpatient hospitalization, regardless of duration, or prolongation of existing In-patient hospitalization - Results in persistent or significant disability or incapacity - Is a congenital anomaly or birth defect in the baby of a woman who received the treatment during pregnancy. - Is judged to be medically significant (this refers to an event that may not be immediately life-threatening or result in death or hospitalization, but may jeopardize the subject or may require medical or surgical intervention to prevent one of the other outcomes listed above) - Any suspected transmission of an infectious agent via the drugs under investigation.

Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction (SUSAR)	Adverse event considered as related to the drugs under investigation, which is both unexpected and serious. SUSARs are subject to expedited reporting to the Competent Authorities and to the Ethics Committees, in compliance with the local regulatory requirements.
Adverse Event of Special Interest (AESI)	In addition to SAE, the following parameters will be monitored: - AE leading to patient's withdrawal - AE of moderate asthma exacerbation - AE of severe asthma exacerbation - Pregnancy cases.

Table 7. Systemic reactions grading system.

Grade	Definition
Grade 0	No symptoms or non-immunotherapy-related symptoms
Grade I	Mild symptoms including localized urticaria, rhinitis or mild asthma symptoms, PEF or FEV1 <20% decrease from baseline
Grade II	Moderate symptoms: slow onset (>15 min) of generalized urticaria and/or moderate asthma symptoms, lung function (PEF or FEV1) <40% decrease from baseline.
Grade III	Severe (non-life-threatening) symptoms: rapid onset (<15 min) of generalized urticaria, angioedema or severe asthma symptoms, lung function (PEF or FEV1) >40% decrease from baseline.
Grade IV	Anaphylactic shock: Immediate evoked reaction of itching, lushing, erythema, generalized urticaria, stridor (angioedema), immediate asthma, hypotension, etc.

7. Statistical analysis

The trial will include 150 subjects following the recommendation of GINA 2023 and EAACI 2019.¹⁴ The number of patients included was based on a power calculation that took into account the expected effect size, the standard deviation of the results, and an ordinal variable for a comparative study of all study arms according to an appropriate formula.¹⁵ A sample size of 35 subjects per arm will be required. Assuming a dropout rate of 15%, 345 subjects with moderate HDM-induced asthma will be screened to obtain 150 patients after randomization.

The intention-to-treat (ITT) population analysis will be performed among all randomized patients in the study; the per-protocol set (PPS) will include subjects who complied with the study treatment; and the safety analysis set will include all the patients who received at least one month of therapy. The Wilcoxon test will be used to analyse differences between the subgroups and individual subgroups at different time points. Categorical variables will be presented as frequencies with percentages. Differences in questionnaire results between subgroups at different time points will be analysed by nonparametric methods. In this part, the Mann-Whitney U test will be used as the main nonparametric analytical method, but the Moses test for extreme reactions will be used

as a supplement. The χ^2 or Fisher's exact test will be used to compare the patient's characteristics at baseline and the occurrence of AEs between the subgroups. A *p* value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

8. References

1. Massanari M, Nelson H, Casale T, Busse W, Kianifard F, Geba GP, et al. Effect of pretreatment with omalizumab on the tolerability of specific immunotherapy in allergic asthma. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2010;125:383–9.
2. Bożek A, Fischer A, Bogacz-Piaseczynska A, Canonica GW. Adding a biologic to allergen immunotherapy increases treatment efficacy. *ERJ Open Res*. 2023;9:00639–2022.
3. Global Initiative for Asthma. Global Strategy for Asthma Management and Prevention (accessed at https://ginasthma.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/GINA-2023-Full-report-23_07_06-WMS.pdf). 2023.
4. Nathan RA, Sorkness CA, Kosinski M, Schatz M, Li JT, Marcus P, et al. Development of the asthma control test: A survey for assessing asthma control. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* [Internet]. 2004 [cited 2024 Apr 18];113:59–65. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S009167490302270X>
5. Schatz M, Kosinski M, Yarlas AS, Hanlon J, Watson ME, Jhingran P. The minimally important difference of the Asthma Control Test. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2009;124:719-723.e1.
6. Juniper EF, O'Byrne PM, Guyatt GH, Ferrie PJ, King DR. Development and validation of a questionnaire to measure asthma control. *Eur Respir J*. 1999;14:902–7.
7. Juniper EF, Svensson K, Mörk AC, Ståhl E. Modification of the asthma quality of life questionnaire (standardised) for patients 12 years and older. *Health Qual Life Outcomes*. 2005;3:58.
8. Juniper EF, Guyatt GH. Development and testing of a new measure of health status for clinical trials in rhinoconjunctivitis. *Clin Exp Allergy*. 1991;21:77–83.
9. Rejestr produktów leczniczych. Actair Summary of Product Characteristics (accessed at: <https://rejestr.ezdrowie.gov.pl/api/rpl/medicinal-products/43435/characteristic>).

10. Demoly P, Corren J, Creticos P, De Blay F, Gevaert P, Hellings P, et al. A 300 IR sublingual tablet is an effective, safe treatment for house dust mite–induced allergic rhinitis: An international, double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomized phase III clinical trial. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2024 Apr 19];147:1020-1030.e10. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0091674920312215>
11. Pfaar O, De Blay F, Canonica GW, Casale TB, Gevaert P, Hellings PW, et al. Clinical benefits with 300 IR HDM SLIT tablet in Europeans with house dust mite allergic rhinitis: Post hoc analysis of a large phase 3 trial. *World Allergy Organ J*. 2024;17:100849.
12. European Medicines Agency. Xolair Summary of Product Characteristics (accessed at: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/product-information/xolair-epar-product-information_en.pdf). Last update: 21/12/2023. 2009.
13. Canonica GW, Baena-Cagnani CE, Bousquet J, Bousquet PJ, Lockey RF, Malling H -J., et al. Recommendations for standardization of clinical trials with Allergen Specific Immunotherapy for respiratory allergy. A statement of a World Allergy Organization (WAO) taskforce. *Allergy* [Internet]. 2007 [cited 2024 Apr 23];62:317–24. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1398-9995.2006.01312.x>
14. Agache I, Lau S, Akdis CA, Smolinska S, Bonini M, Cavkaytar O, et al. EAACI Guidelines on Allergen Immunotherapy: House dust mite-driven allergic asthma. *Allergy*. 2019;74:855–73.
15. Chow SC, Shao J, Wang H, Lokhnygina Y. *Sample Size Calculations in Clinical Research: Third Edition* [Internet]. 3rd ed. Chow SC, Shao J, Wang H, Lokhnygina Y, editors. Boca Raton: Chapman and Hall/CRC; 2017 [cited 2024 Jul 2]. Available from: <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/9781351727129>